

GIDROFIL-GIDROFOB POLYMER KOMPOZITLARNING XOSSALARINI TAHLILI

Sattarkulov Lazizbek Abror o'g'li

Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti

4-bosqich talabasi

E-mail: lazizbeksattarkulov@gmail.com

Egamberdiyev Elmurod Abduqodirovich

Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti

Texnika fanlari doktori, professor

E-mail: el0919@mail.com

Sotvoldiyeva Yulduz Farxod qizi

Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti

2-bosqich talabasi

E-mail: yulduzsotiboldiyeva604@gmail.com

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada gidrofil-gidrofob polymer kompozitlarining xossalari tahlil qilingan. Maqolada nazariy ilmiy tadqiqotlarning fikrlari va amaliy hisob-kitoblar ko'rsatilgan. Shuningdek adsorbtsiyasining o'ziga xosligi, u adsorbentlarni nisbatan yaqin solishtirma sirt yuzasi va g'ovakligini aniqlashning imkoni mavjudligi haqida so'z boradi. Xulosa qismida MTMS dan sintez qilingan kam zichlikka ega bo'lgan keremnezemning kuchli gidrofoblik xususiyati aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: gidrofil-gidrofob, selluloza tola, adsorbent, kremnezem.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье проанализированы свойства гидрофильно-гидрофобных полимерных композитов. В статье приведены мнения теоретических научных исследований и практических расчетов. Также говорится о специфике адсорбции, возможности определения относительной площади поверхности и пористости адсорбентов. В заключение следует отметить, что керамика низкой плотности, синтезированная из МТМС, обладает сильными гидрофобными свойствами.

Ключевые слова: гидрофильно-гидрофобные, целлюлозное волокно, адсорбент, кремнезем.

ANNOTATION

This article analyzes the properties of hydrophilic-hydrophobic polymer composites. The article shows the opinions of theoretical scientific research and practical calculations. It also talks about the specificity of adsorption, the possibility of determining the relative surface area and porosity of adsorbents. In conclusion, low-density ceramic synthesized from MTMS has strong hydrophobic properties

Key words: *hydrophilic-hydrophobic, cellulose fiber, adsorbent, silica.*

So‘nggi yillarda gidrofoblik xususiyatiga ega bo‘lgan silikogellar sinteziga bo‘lgan qiziqish ortib bormoqda. Bunga sabab ularning sanoat tarmoqlarida ishlatilish sohasining ko‘pligida va ularning bardoshi hamda namlikka chidamli ekanligidir. Metiltrimetoksisilan (MTMS) yordamida tayyorlangan eritma past katalizator konsentratsiyasida (<1 M) gellanmaydi, chunki kondensatsiya uchun mavjud bo‘lgan Si-OH guruhlar kamroq, ular bir-biri bilan sekin reaksiyaga kirishadilar. Biroq, yuqori katalizator konsentratsiyasi uchun (≥ 2 M), kondensatsiya reaksiyalarining tezligi oshishi bilan gellanish jarayoni ham tezroq boradi. 1-rasmda ko‘rinib turganidek, izotermaning egri chiziqlari boshlang‘ich maydon bosimining o‘o‘qiga nisbatan, erituvchida cheksiz aralashadigan shishasimon polimerlarga xos bo‘lgan, P/P_s son qiymatlari yuqorilashgan qismida qavariq S-simon tuzilishga ega.

Polisaxaridlar qattiq zanjirli polimerdir va u suvda faqat bo‘kadi, uning suvga munosabati mahsulot olish va kimyoviy modifikatsiyasi tufayli to‘liq o‘rganilgan. Ma‘lumki, selluloza kapillyar-g‘ovakli kolloid moddalar sinfiga kiradi va mikrokapillyarlarining keng rivojlangan tashqi va ichki sirti, tor g‘ovak bo‘shliqlar bilan tavsiflanadi. Selluloza tolalarining tartibsiz tuzilishi tufayli g‘ovaklar fibrillararo va ichki fibrillar bo‘shliqlarda hosil bo‘lishi mumkin.

Ular turli konfiguratsiya va o‘lchamlarga ega. Mikro g‘ovaklar mikro birikmalarga kiradigan nanofibrillarning nomuntazam taxlanishi sababli paydo bo‘ladi, sellulozaning qo‘shni mikrofibrillar orasida mezo g‘ovaklar hosil bo‘ladi.

Adsorbentlarni sirt yuzasidagi funktsional guruhlar bilan kvadrupol-dipol ta‘sirlashuv natijasida ularning sirt yuzasida adsorbtsiyalanuvchi suvni adsorbtsiyasini o‘rganish alohida qiziq ish kasb etadi. Suv adsorbtsiyasining o‘ziga xosligi u adsorbentlarni nisbatan yaqin solishtirma sirt yuzasini va g‘ovakligini aniqlash imkonini beradi. Ma‘lumki, turli xil adsorbentlarning sorbtsion qobiliyati sezilarli darajada o‘zlarining kristall, kapillyar-g‘ovak tuzilishi va makro molekulalarining molekulyar taxlanishiga bog‘liq. Asosiy mezonlarni qanoatlantiruvchi Brunauer-Emmet-Teller (BET) nazariyasi ilmiy tadqiqotlar va amaliy xisob-kitoblarda keng tarqalgan. Shuning uchun, unga xos bo‘lgan cheklovlarga alohida axamiyat berish zarur:

- yuzaning energetik turli xilligini xisobga olmaydi;
- nazariya, yuqori qiymatli bosim (kapilyar kondensatsiyani xisobga olmagan holda) $P_i/P_i^0 > 0.3$ soha uchun qo'llab bo'lmaydi, shuning uchun u faqat $0,05 < P_i/P_i^0 < 0.3$ sohada qo'llaniladi;
- kondensatsiya tushunchalariga asoslangan BET nazariyasi faqat bug'larning adsorbtsiyalanish tavsifi uchun qo'llaniladi, shuning uchun u gazlar adsorbtsiyalanishida ishlatilmaydi.

Adsorbentlarning struktura adsorbtsion ko'rsatkichlardan solishtirma yuzasi (S) BET nazariyasi tenglamasi yordamida aniqlandi. Bunda ordinata $P/P_s/a(1 - P/P_s)$ va abtssisa o'qida P/P_s qiymatlari qo'yilsa to'g'ri chiziqli koordinatalar hosil bo'ladi (1-rasm).

1-rasm: SEAS va NaKMS aralashmasining (1)SEAS; 2)4/1; 3)3/2; 4)2/3; 5)1/4; 6)NaKMS): suv bug'lari sorbsiyasining BET bo'yicha adsorbtsiya izotermalari

1-jadval

Namunalarning suv bug'ini adsorbtsiyalash izotermalari bo'yicha hisoblangan kapilyar-g'ovaklik ko'rsatkichlari

No	Namuna	$X_m, g/g$	r_{or}, A	$W_o, sm^3/g$	$S_{sol} sm^2/g$	C	$-\Delta g, J/mol$	$-\Delta G J/mol$
1	SEAS	0,273	105,22	8,2	1597,33	12,6	116,52	580
2	SEAS-NaKMS (4:1) nisbatda	1,515	25,68	11,4	8881,23	4,25	140,61	765
3	SEAS-NaKMS (3:2) nisbatda	0,735	11,46	24,0	4306,63	5,44	104,96	492
4	SEAS-NaKMS (2:3) nisbatda	0,345	354,41	33,7	2020,27	8,88	68,33	34
5	SEAS-NaKMS (1:4) nisbatda	0,503	226,56	35,8	2948,52	6,85	86,15	540
6	NaKMS	1,143	143,28	48,0	6700,05	3,55	93,52	620

Brunauer-Emmet Teller usuli bo'yicha suv bug'ini adsorbtsiyasi izotermalari asosida o'rganilgan namunalar SEAS, NaKMS va ular asosidagi aralashmalarni monoqavatlar sig'imi X_m , energetic konstantasi C , solishtirma sirt yuzasi S_{ud} , adsorbtsiyaning maksimal ($P_i/P_i^0=1$) miqdori bo'yicha g'ovaklarning hajmiy yig'indisi W_o va g'ovakni o'rtacha radiusi $r_{o'r}$ aniqlandi ular quydagi 1-jadvalda keltirilgan.

Suvning sorbtsiyalanish tadqiqoti natijalari uning namunalarini: SEAS-NaKMS (4:1), SEAS-NaKMS (3:2), SEAS-NaKMS (1:4) SEAS-NaKMS (2:3), SEAS, NaKMS mono qavat sig'imi va solishtirma sirt yuzasining kamayib borish tartibida joylashtirish mumkinligini ko'rsatdi. Buerdan SEAS-NaKMS (4:1), NaKMS, o'zida mono qavatli sig'im X_m va solishtirma sirt yuza S_{sol} ga nisbatan katta qiymatli mikro g'ova ktuzilishni ifodalaydi ,deb xulosa qilish mumkin.

Metil trimetoksisilandan sintez qilingan kremnezemning SEM (x2000) tasvirlari keltirilgan bo'lib, mikroskopik morfologiyasi 2-rasmda keltirilgan bo'lib kremnezemning skeletining diametiri 20 mm tavsiflangan. Kremnezemning ikkilamchi zarrachalarining bir-birining ustiga qoplashi natijasida hosil bo'lgan marjon qoyalari zanjiriga o'xshash tarmoq tuzulishiga ega. Skelet zarrachalarining aloqasi nisbatan yaqin joylashganini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

2-rasm. MTMS asosida olingan gidrofil kremnezemning 2000 marta kattalshtirilgan SEM tasviri

3-rasm. MTMS asosida olingan gidrofil kremnezemda atomlarning tarqalish xaritalari

3-rasmda MTMS asosida olingan gidrofil kremnezemda atomlarning tarqalish xaritalari keltirilgan bo'lib, unda polymer tarkibiga kiruvchi element atomlarining tekis tarqalganligini hamda namunaning sirt morfologiyasini takrorlaganini ko'ramiz.

4-rasm. MTMS asosida olingan gidrofil kremnezemning EDS

4-rasmda namunaning energiya dispersion spektri (EDS) keltirilgan. Namunaning EDSda elementlar miqdoriy ko'rsatkichlari keltirilgan bo'lib, unda uglerod 24%, kislorod 35,99%, kremniy 39,99% ni tashkil etganligi ko'rinadi.

5-rasm. MTMS asosida sintez qilingan gidrofob kremnezem SEM suratlari: A - x300, B – x600, C - x1000, D – x3000, E – x10000 marta kattalashtirilgan.

MTMS dan sintez qilingan kam zichlikka ega bo‘lgan keremnezemning kuchli gidrofoblik xususiyati aniqlandi 5-rasmda uning turli o‘lchamlarda olingan SEM tasvirlari keltirgan bo‘lib kremnezemning yuqorida ko‘rilgan marjon ko‘rinishlari orasiga kremnezem polimer plonkaga o‘xshash struktura orqali kirib borganini ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Bunda qoyalar orasida masofalar kattalashib, g‘ovaklashgani yaqqol ko‘rinadi.

6-rasm. MTMS asosida sintez qilingan gidrofob kremnezem EDS

6-rasmda elementlar miqdoriy ko'rsatkichlari keltirilgan bo'lib uglerod 26%, kislorod 34,99%, kremniy 38,99% ni tashkil etganligi malum bo'ldi.

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